

relatively fast compared with sunn hemp and dhaincha. Every kilogram of P applied at 13 kg/ha produced 108 kg grain in cowpea, 85 in dhaincha, 89 in

sunn hemp, and 67 in fallow plots, showing an increase of 18-41 kg grain/kg P over fallow plots (see table).

Green manuring saved about 13 kg P/

ha and contributed to extra grain yield. Cowpea was the best green manure crop for rice. ■

Crop management

Effect of tillage on physical properties of soil and yield of peanut in a rice-based cropping system

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Farmers in southern India, particularly in Andhra Pradesh, grow peanut after wet season puddled rice. In the rhizosphere, peanut requires a physical environment entirely different from that of rice. Inadequate peanut seedbed preparation in puddled soils results in poor germination, plant stand, growth, and yield.

We studied the effect of five tillage methods (see table) for irrigated peanut after puddled rice during 1988-89 and 1989-90 wet seasons. The experiment

was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications in a sandy loam soil with 0.11% organic C.

Plowing was deeper in the tractor-drawn treatment. Mean weight diameter (MWD) of seed zone aggregates varied among the tillage treatments. MWD, with many clods, was highest with the country plow. The rototiller treatment had small and relatively uniform aggregates.

Tillage affected germination. It was highest with the rototiller, where aggregate sizes favored good seed-soil contact and the highest soil moisture content. Soil penetration resistance recorded at pegging stage was least in the rototiller treatment. Haulm and pod yields were highest in the tractor-drawn treatment, closely followed by those with the rototiller.

The higher yields obtained with tractor tillage compared with bullock-drawn treatments might be due to the deeper plowing, which resulted in breaking of

the subsoil hardpan layer and smaller aggregates. Higher yields with rototillage were due to uniform aggregate size and low soil strength (penetration resistance).

We suggest that farmers use rototillage when growing peanut after puddled rice in light-textured soils because of the relative ease of operation, low cost, and higher yields. ■

Effect of tillage on physical properties of soil and yield of peanut. Hyderabad, India, 1988 and 1989.

Treatment	Plowing depth (cm)	Mean weight diameter (cm)	Soil moisture ^a (% wt/wt)	Germination (%)	Penetration resistance at pegging stage (kg/cm ²)	Yield (t/ha)	
						Haulm	Pod
T1 Plowing twice with bullock-drawn, country plow	7.0	4.5	7.4	47	35	2.39	1.44
T1 + disc harrow twice, bullock drawn	7.1	3.0	7.9	51	33	2.52	1.45
T1 + disc harrow 4 times, bullock drawn	7.8	2.3	7.2	52	35	2.54	1.70
T1 + rototiller twice, power tiller drawn	7.6	1.6	11.3	57	29	3.13	1.90
T5 Disc plow once + disc harrow once, tractor drawn	12.9	3.0	10.7	55	31	3.20	1.96
LSD (0.05)	-	-	1.3	6	1	0.35	0.11

^aSoil moisture at 20 d after sowing.

Evaluation of rice planting methods for rainfed lowlands of Karnataka

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Rice is normally sown with a seed drill in the rainfed lowlands of interior Karnataka. Sowing dry seed on moist soil with the onset of the monsoon (DSR-moist) is the common practice, with dry sowing on dry soil (DSR-dry) seen in some areas. Wet sowing can be difficult

Grain yield and net profit as influenced by planting methods of rice in rainfed lowlands of Karnataka, India, 1990 and 1991 kharifs.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Net profit (\$/ha)	
	1990	1991	1990	1991
Wet sown without fertilizer	4.3	F	10.7	F
Wet sown with fertilizer	5.6	F	13.6	F
Dry sown without fertilizer	N	4.5	N	14.5
Dry sown with fertilizer	5.2	6.1	12.4	21.2
Line transplanted with fertilizer	5.0	5.6	10.8	17.2
Broadcast pre-germinated seeds with fertilizer	1.8	F	0.9	F
LSD (0.05)	1.2	1.3		

^aN = treatment not included, F = failed treatment.